

Ameliorating Energy Efficiency in Wireless Sensor Networks: Integrating the Syracuse Algorithm with K-MEAN for Enhanced Base Station Mobile Management

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ABSTRACT

In designing sensor networks for hostile environments, energy conservation at each sensor node is a critical challenge. This study proposes a novel deployment of two mobile base stations utilizing Syracuse's modified algorithm, alongside the original algorithm, to predict breakpoints. The approach aims to extend the sensor network's lifespan by leveraging terrain dimensions to identify effective appointment points based on Syracuse's conjecture. We define four metrics to evaluate the proposed solution. Simulation results indicate that implementing multiple mobile base stations, guided by the Syracuse conjecture, significantly enhances the overall lifespan of the sensor network.

KEYWORDS

Syracuse, Wireless Network, Mobile Network, SHEM, algorithm

1. INTRODUCTION

A sensor network is a fixed ad hoc network with numerous sensor nodes deployed for unattended operation. Each sensor node has a detection device, a low-capacity processing unit, a short-range wireless transceiver, and limited energy from a battery. The sensor nodes monitor environmental phenomena, process the acquired data, and transmit it to a base station located at the edge of the sensor network. The base station collects the data from the sensor nodes and transmits it to a remote-control station. Most research models of sensor networks consider a single static base station located at the edge of the sensor network [2],[14] [15].

In studies [1], and [2], experimental evidence was presented demonstrating that sensor nodes located one hop away from a base station deplete their energy more rapidly compared to other nodes in the network. This is because these nodes not only transmit their messages but also relay messages from numerous other nodes. Consequently, these sensor nodes exhaust their energy quickly, rendering them inoperative. This energy depletion results in communication failures between many sensor nodes and the base stations, ultimately causing the network to become inoperable.

According to research outlined in projects [1] and [2], nodes located near the base station experience a faster depletion of energy when transmitting larger volumes of data.

To address this issue, the use of mobile base stations has been proposed as a means to achieve a more balanced energy consumption. However, it has been observed that positioning the base station along the perimeter of the detection field, as suggested in [5] and [6], can lead to higher average network power consumption due to the necessity for nodes to communicate with the mobile base stations via multi-hop routes. Additionally, the dynamic path changes of the base stations require additional overhead to maintain an efficient network topology.

In [7], the performance of the base station (BS) is characterized using the random mobility model. References [8] and [9] introduce various heuristics aimed at optimizing the BS movement to ensure timely visitation of the source nodes and prevent buffer overflows. Although this strategy reduces power consumption by minimizing multi-hop wireless transmissions, it results in increased latency when gathering data from extensive detection fields due to the slower movement of the BS.

In clustered wireless sensor networks (WSNs), cluster heads tend to deplete their power more quickly than other nodes, leading to premature failure. Thus, it is crucial to distribute the load of the sensor nodes among the cluster heads to extend the network's longevity. This challenge is recognized as the load-balanced clustering problem, which falls under the category of NP-hard problems [10], [17], [20].

Cluster heads (CHs) bear a heavier load than regular sensor nodes. If CHs are chosen from regular sensor nodes, they will expire sooner than other nodes in the network.

The main problem with clustering is non-uniform clustering which leads to high power dissipation from the sensor node, increased total power consumption, and unsecured network connectivity [11], [12], [18], [19].

The K-means algorithm serves as the primary method for clustering. In this algorithm, the cluster head is chosen to prolong the overall lifespan of the network [14]. The authors delineated the entire process into three phases. The LEACH protocol is employed to determine the initial CH selection. Subsequently, the network is segmented into k clusters based on the Euclidean distance, and nodes join their nearest CH. After the nodes join the CH, the center of each cluster is determined, and each node is assigned an ID based on its distance from the centroid. Nodes closer to the center will have a smaller number. The CH is then rotated, and the next node that is relatively closer to the center is selected as the new CH. This approach enhances the overall network lifetime compared to other schemes, but the periodic reformation of clusters results in additional network overhead and high energy consumption. Furthermore, since clusters are initially formed randomly, this can lead to suboptimal clusters and uneven distribution of the load.

In this [4], the deployment of multiple base stations can effectively decrease the average distance between source-sink pairs, thereby prolonging the network's lifespan and enabling increased data transmission over time. A critical factor in this multi-base station approach is determining the best locations for these base stations to maximize the network's lifespan.

Dans [7], le problème de placement des stations de base est formulé comme un problème d'optimisation et les emplacements optimaux des stations de base sont obtenus comme solution à un programme linéaire en nombres entiers.

2. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

2.1. Block diagram

Figure 1 model 1

Figure 2 model 2

2.2. Algorithms

2.2.1. Algorithm 1 The main principles of our algorithm for a fixed network

- a. Use of the Syracuse conjuncture
- b. Convert the length of the field into an integer
- c. Determination of the position of the two base stations relative to the size of the field
- d. Determination of the number of clusters based on the number of sensors to deploy
- e. Determination of the possible positions of the Heads clusters
- f. Application of the K-MEAN algorithm
- g. The CHs communicate with the two central base stations.
- h. Use Syracuse original to find the stopping points of the two mobile stations in reverse directions

2.2.2. Algorithm 2: the Syracuse equation

The authors of [8] emphasize that "determining the sufficient number of guards to cover the entire art gallery is an NP Hard optimization problem". We use the Syracuse equation to determine the number of clusters and clusters heads.

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{x}{2}, & \text{si } x \text{ est pair} \\ 3x + 1, & \text{si } x \text{ est impair} \end{cases}$$

We will modify this algorithm with the following expression:

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{x}{2}, & \text{si } x \text{ est pair} \\ (3x + 1)/2, & \text{si } x \text{ est impair} \end{cases}$$

2.2.3. Algorithm 3: Determining the number of clusters or cluster-head N is the number of sensors to be deployed on the ground.

Function syracuse(N):

Begin

u = N

n=0

While (u! = 1) do

 If (u%2) ==0 :

 u = u/2

 Else

 u = (3*u+1)//2

 endif

 n=n+1

endwhile

return n

end

2.2.4. Algorithm 4: Determining the position of the two base stations based on the size of the terrain

N is the length of the deployment terrain

Function search (N: integer)

Begin

 max_time=0;

 for n from 1 to N do

 flight_time= syracuse(n)

 if flight_time>max_time then

 max_time:=flight_time;

 Nmax:=n;

 Endif

 endfor;

 return(Nmax)

End

2.2.5. Algorithm 5: Determination of possible positions of cluster heads based on the number of sensors to deploy.

```
(N number of sensors to deploy)
Tps_vol=[]
for nb in range(2, tps_vol_syracuse(N)):
    if (tps_vol_syracuse(nb) not in tps_vol):
        tps_vol.append((nb, tps_vol_syracuse(nb)))
    endif
endfor
```

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Parameter of simulation [14]

Parameter	Value
Initial energy	2J
E_{elec}	50nJ/bit
E_{amp}	0.0013pJ/bit/m ²
Data packet size	4000 byte
Energy taken for aggregation (Epa)	5nJ/bit/signal

The transmitter consumes:

$$E_t(k, d) = E_{elec} * k + E_{amp} * k * d^2$$

and the receiver consumes:

$$E_r(k) = E_{elec}(k) = E_{elec} * k$$

3.2. Simulation

We utilized multiple terrain sizes to display diverse base station positions while maintaining a consistent number k of clusters based on the number of sensors.

When deploying 200 sensors, the positions of the cluster heads are determined as depicted in the diagram below (figure 2). These positions seem to be distributed in such a way that they cover the entire terrain.

Figure 2 Deployment of 200 sensors

In a previous study, we analyzed model 1 on the left. We appreciated the positions of the clusters and the base stations. Solution 2 on the right uses a mobility of the two base stations by showing the stopping points thanks to the original version of Syracuse. These positions are of interest and bring the base stations closer to the cluster heads (CH). The positions provided by the Syracuse conjuncture show an appreciable advantage.

For several 400 sensors to be deployed, we obtain the positions of the cluster heads according to the following diagram figure 3.

Compared to Figure 2, we see almost the same advantages for moving from the base station to the HC. The positions seem to be advantageous to avoid a long transmission of the CHs. This allows the CH to save their energy.

Figure 3: Deployment of 400 sensors

3.2. Analysis of energy consumption

- Using 200 sensors, and comparing our algorithm model 1 to model 2, we obtain the following Figure 4. We note that on the whole of the energy consumed, model 2 spends less energy than model 1. This is explained by the reduction of the sending distance by bringing the mobile base stations closer to the CHs.

Figure 4: schema of energy

- When we repeated the study using 300 sensor nodes, the resulting plot clearly showed that Model 2 has better energy management capabilities compared to Model 1. The shape of the two curves further illustrates the energy savings achieved by relocating the two base stations to the positions depicted in Figure 3.

Figure 5: schema of energy

- In our experiment, we utilized 400 sensor nodes to evaluate the energy management of our two models. As depicted in Figure 6, the curves align closely with those in Figures 5 and 4, indicating a consistent pattern. This reaffirms the superiority of Model 2 over Model 1.

Figure 6: schema of energy

4. CONCLUSIONS

The second algorithm model is more effective at improving the energy efficiency of sensor networks compared to the first model. Both models utilize the Syracuse conjecture and the K-MEANS algorithm to identify the optimal number of clusters and potential positions of CHs, thereby contributing to energy conservation in the sensor network. The second model enhances the first model by introducing mobility to the two base stations, allowing them to calculate meeting points and reduce the transmission distance of CHs.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank everyone, just everyone!

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